

Supplementary material

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In this supplement we include results of additional studies to validate the models and understand their fundamental properties. In particular, we investigate the sensitivity of the results to varying fiber angles, verify that the obtained finite element meshes match the original images, and investigate the load-independence of the contractility parameter and general force-length relationship of the chosen model.

1 Fiber angle Sensitivity

In order to determine the sensitivity of our simulation pipeline to the choice of fiber angle, for each patient we tested a total of 16 different fiber angles using symmetric angles on the endo-/ epicardium of 45/-45, 60/-60, 70/-70 and 80/-80 degrees, allowing the RV and LV to vary independently. It should be noted that histological studies, see for instance [1], indicate that fiber angles vary from about 60 degrees on the endocardium to about -60 degrees on the epicardium.

Figure 1: Average and standard deviation of optimal angles for minimizing circumferential strain misfit in the control and PAH cohorts in both the LV and the RV.

All choices of fiber angles could accurately reproduce pressure volume relationships, and the misfit of the volumes were largely insensitive to the choice. We therefore selected the optimal fiber angle based on the misfit with the circumferential strain. Average and spread of the resulting optimal choice of fiber angles are shown in Figure 1, with average

optimal angle centered around 60/60 for all conditions except for the control LV, which achieved better fit of the circumferential strain with an average higher epicardial and endocardial figure angle. Resulting fits of the peak circumferential and longitudinal strain for the measurements, 60/60 fiber configuration, and optimal fiber choice are shown in figures 2 together with summary plots of RV contractility results when using 60/60 and optimal angles.

Figure 2: Comparison of peak circumferential (top row) and longitudinal (middle row) strains between measurements, models using optimized fiber angles, and models using 60/60 fiber orientations for the cohort of normal patients (left) and PAH patients (right). (Bottom) Comparison of calculated RV peak active strain as a function of RV volume ratios for simulations using 60/60 fiber angles (left), and optimized fiber angles (right)

2 Sensitivity to pericardial spring boundary condition

We tested the sensitivity to the value of the Robin type boundary condition on the epicardium. In the original manuscript, the value of this parameter was set to 0.5 kPa / cm². For this sensitivity analysis, we picked the spring constant values 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, and 2.0 kPa / cm² to represent the stiffness of the pericardium, and performed the full optimization pipeline on all the patients. The peak contractility as a function of the pericardial spring constant is shown in Figure 3. We observe that an increase in the spring constant value produce an increase in the peak contractility. This behavior is present because the contractility has to be increased in order to counteract the forces generated by the increased stiffness of the Robin boundary condition at the epicardium to fit the motion data.

Figure 3: Peak contractility as a function of the pericardial spring constant. Each frame displays the mean peak contractility (dots) as well as the standard deviation within each group (vertical lines) are shown for different value of the spring constant.

3 Sensitivity of passive stiffness to diastolic pressures

The lack of diastolic pressure measurements for the control subjects might raise the question whether the optimized material parameters would be significantly different if

diastolic pressure measurements were available.

To address this question, we estimated the resulting passive material parameters using perturbed values of the prescribed diastolic pressure. Specifically, all the diastolic pressures were perturbed by $\pm 20\%$, $\pm 10\%$, and $\pm 5\%$ and new material parameters were estimated in each case using the same original volumes as target. The resulting optimized material parameters as well as the relative difference between the optimized material parameters and the optimized material parameters with no perturbation are shown in Figure 4. We observe that by increasing the diastolic pressure, we need a stiffer material to obtain the same volume, i.e., a higher value of a_{LV} . Furthermore, we observe that the relative change in material parameters is of the same magnitude as the perturbation in the diastolic pressures except for one outlier for CASE2.

Figure 4: Left: The optimized material parameters for control subjects obtained using diastolic pressure data that has been perturbed by $\pm 20\%$, $\pm 10\%$, and $\pm 5\%$. Right: Relative difference between the optimized material parameters and the optimized material parameters with no perturbation.

4 Validation results

In this section we present additional figures used in the validation of the personalized mechanical models. Figure 5 shows summary figures for active strain for all cases through all regions, as well as resulting PV loops for each of the control and PH cases. Figure 6 shows the finite element meshes overlaid with the original images, for all cases at end of diastole (ED), start of ejection (SE) and end of systole (ES). Although some minor differences may be observed, all meshes show a good fit with the images.

Figure 5: Left: RV, LV, and septal active contraction parameters over the time course of the optimization for both the healthy controls (top row), and the PH patients (middle and bottom row). Right: Corresponding PV loops for all control and PH patients for both the LV (red) and the RV (blue). Open circles denote measurements and solid lines represent simulations.

Figure 6: The figure shows the finite element meshes overlaying the original images, for all cases and at three different time points of the cardiac cycle.

5 Optimization under alternative loading conditions.

Here we synthetically demonstrate that a unique twitch can in theory be reconstructed under different loading conditions. For this case, we use the inverted gamma trace from one of the optimized models, and then perform forward modelling using the same mesh and active strain waveform, but with different scaling on the diastolic and systolic loadings. The goal is to produce a range of result-

ing PV loops but with the same underlying cardiac twitch dynamics, which when inverted in our framework, reproduces this same underlying behavior.

For this test, a forward model built using the inversion results was taken as a starting point. This simulation consists of a patient mesh that was subjected to a pressure loading trace and with a corresponding active strain twitch that produced a PV loop and calculated strain profiles. The loading was then scaled up and down by 50% in this forward model to produce new PV loops, Figure 7, and corresponding calculated strains. These PV loops and strains from the perturbed simulations were then inverted again using our methodology into active strain traces. We can see from this synthetic study that the same twitch is reconstructed using the algorithm independent of the diastolic and systolic loading. We also plot a sample of some parameter trajectories for these simulations during optimization in figure 8, showing that the parameters for active contraction rapidly converge to a stable value for each of the loading cases.

Figure 7: Left: PVs for alternative loading conditions and the same geometric mesh and active strain waveform. Resulting twitches from optimization of PV loops and resulting circumferential strain.

Figure 8: RV, LV, and septal active contraction parameter trajectories over optimization for one time point in the PV loops from Figure 7.

6 Investigation of the force-length relationship

The force-length relationship, where active force increases as the muscle is stretched, is a characteristic feature of muscle tissue. In the active stress approach

to cardiac mechanics, and in particular in models aiming to replicate the contraction biophysics, the force-velocity relation is often explicitly included as a function of myofilament overlap. With the active strain approach applied here, passive and active stresses are effectively merged into one, and the force-length relation is less explicit. This model choice was made to minimize the number of fitted parameters, while being able to extract macroscopic stress quantities characterizing the local contraction and loading state of the tissue. However, it is still of interest to see how well the model captures this essential property of cardiac muscle biophysics.

6.1 Unidirectional stretch and contraction

We study the force-length relationship of the proposed active strain model in a controlled and simplified setting. Consider the active contraction model

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{F}_a.$$

with $\mathbf{F}_a = \text{diag}((1 - \gamma), (1 - \gamma)^{-1/2}, (1 - \gamma)^{-1/2})$, where γ is a parameter describing active muscle shortening (active strain). We here consider the simple case of a tissue cube with uniform fiber orientation aligned with the x -axis. The cube is loaded with a tension T in the x -direction, and is unloaded in the transverse directions. This results in a uniform deformation state with a diagonal deformation gradient. Assuming tissue incompressibility, we can write the deformation gradient as $\mathbf{F} = \text{diag}(\lambda, \lambda^{-1/2}, \lambda^{-1/2})$, with λ being the stretch in the fiber direction. The elastic component of the deformation gradient, \mathbf{F}_e , is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_e = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}_a^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda(1 - \gamma)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda^{-1/2}(1 - \gamma)^{1/2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda^{-1/2}(1 - \gamma)^{1/2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

From the decomposition of \mathbf{F} we can compute a corresponding decomposition of the right Cauchy-Green tensor. We have

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} = (\mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{F}_a)^T (\mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{F}_a) = \mathbf{F}_a^T \mathbf{F}_e^T \mathbf{F}_e \mathbf{F}_a = \mathbf{F}_a^T \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{F}_a.$$

With the deformation state considered here, \mathbf{C}_e is diagonal with components

$$\begin{aligned} C_{e,11} &= \lambda^2(1 - \gamma)^{-2}, \\ C_{e,22} &= C_{e,33} = \lambda^{-1}(1 - \gamma). \end{aligned}$$

The chosen strain-energy density (Eq. (3) in the main text) yields the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress as

$$\mathbf{S} = 2 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} - p \mathbf{C}^{-1} = 2 \sum_{i=1,4f} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial I_i} \frac{\partial I_i}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} - p \mathbf{C}^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where I_1, I_{4f} are invariants of \mathbf{C}_e , given by

$$I_1 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}_e), \quad I_{4f} = \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot (\mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{f}_0),$$

with \mathbf{f}_0 being a unit vector aligned with the fiber orientation. We have in general

$$\frac{\partial I_1}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} = \mathbf{I}, \quad \frac{\partial I_{4f}}{\partial \mathbf{C}_e} = \mathbf{f}_0 \otimes \mathbf{f}_0,$$

and from (1) we get

$$\mathbf{S} = ae^{b(I_1-3)}\mathbf{I} + 2a_f(I_{4f} - 1)e^{b_f(I_{4f}-1)^2}\mathbf{f}_0 \otimes \mathbf{f}_0 - p\mathbf{C}^{-1}$$

and finally the Cauchy stress

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = ae^{b(I_1-3)}\mathbf{F}\mathbf{F}^T + 2a_f(I_{4f} - 1)e^{b_f(I_{4f}-1)^2}\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{f}_0 \otimes \mathbf{f}_0)\mathbf{F}^T - p\mathbf{I}. \quad (2)$$

For the deformation state considered here, the invariants I_1 and I_{4f} read

$$I_1 = \lambda^2(1 - \gamma)^{-2} + 2\lambda^{-1}(1 - \gamma), \quad (3)$$

$$I_{4f} = \lambda^2(1 - \gamma)^{-2}, \quad (4)$$

and the resulting Cauchy stress tensor is diagonal with the following components:

$$\sigma_{11} = ae^{b(I_1-3)}\lambda^2 + 2a_f(I_{4f} - 1)e^{b_f(I_{4f}-1)^2}\lambda^2 - p, \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{33} = ae^{b(I_1-3)}\lambda^{-1} - p. \quad (6)$$

Since the cube is unloaded and therefore stress free in the transverse directions, (6) gives

$$p = ae^{b(I_1-3)}\lambda^{-1},$$

and we can insert this into (5) to get

$$\sigma_{11} = ae^{b(I_1-3)}(\lambda^2 - \lambda^{-1}) + 2a_f(I_{4f} - 1)e^{b_f(I_{4f}-1)^2}\lambda^2. \quad (7)$$

This gives an explicit relation between active strain γ , fiber shortening λ and fiber stress σ_{11} . For a known tension T and active strain γ we can compute the resulting λ , and likewise if we know γ and λ we can compute the corresponding tension and fiber stress.

6.2 Contraction against a serial elastic force

We want to use (7) to explore the length-tension relationship of our active model. As input, we have used the fitted γ trace for one of the patients, shown in the left panel of Figure 9. Using the force formulation in (7), we now consider a cube of tissue which is first pre-stretched to a given λ , and then contracts against a linear spring force. The resulting balance equation is

$$\sigma_{tissue} + \sigma_{preload} + \sigma_{series} = 0,$$

where σ_{tissue} is the combined active and passive stress given by (7), $\sigma_{preload}$ is the stress required to stretch the passive cube to a given λ_0 , i.e.,

$$\sigma_{preload} = \sigma_{tissue}(\lambda = \lambda_0, \gamma = 0),$$

and σ_{series} is given by

$$\sigma_{series} = k_{se}(\lambda - \lambda_0).$$

Here, k_{se} is the spring stiffness. We have chosen $k_{se} = 50$, which gives reasonable contraction dynamics for the tissue.

The right panel of Figure 9 shows the resulting dynamic λ values, for a series of initial stretch values $\lambda_0 = 0.9, \dots, 1.2$. To illustrate the behaviour of the active strain model, we also plot the quantity $1 - \gamma$ in the same plot. For an unloaded and freely contracting tissue cube, we would have $\lambda = 1 - \gamma$, while for the loaded cases, the two will differ but follow the same pattern.

The resulting forces are shown in the left panel of Figure 10. The traces show the $\sigma_{tissue} - \sigma_{preload}$ for each of the stretch values. The right panel shows the relation between λ_0 and the maximum force value.

Figure 9: Left: Trace of γ from one of the patients, used as input to the simple active model. Right: The resulting traces of the total fiber stretch λ , for different values of initial stretch. For reference, we also plot $1 - \gamma$ as an illustration of the “preferred” active contraction state.

Figure 10: Left: Force twitches for λ in the range from 0.9 to 1.2. Right: The relation between maximum force and λ_0 .

References

- [1] Daniel D Streeter Jr, Henry M Spotnitz, Dali P Patel, John Ross Jr, and Edmund H Sonnenblick. Fiber orientation in the canine left ventricle during diastole and systole. *Circulation research*, 24(3):339–347, 1969.